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Legacy of Colonial Feudal Architecture in the Perspective of the Teota Zaminadar Palace.

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Architecture of Bangladesh has been evolved throughout the ages of ambitious external influences with the indigenous ingredients of the deltaic culture and climate. In this long evolutionary process, a new architectural style and construction technology was introduced in the concepts and continuity of the architecture of Bengal in colonial period. The western allied Bengal Feudal lord/ Zamindar along with the upper class society patronized the colonial practices and flourished a new architectural style in their living units. This new Architecture has distinct aesthetic value and considered as a rich evidence of permanent residential construction all over the country in vast numbers. Though comprising of distinct architectural style and a fusion of external and local cultures, these structures have been poorly addressed in the study of architectural history and heritage. This paper is an attempt to make a comprehensive study of context, socio-cultural aspects and the architectural development of this particular house form with a case study to test the findings.

Introduction

The development of architectural styles in Bangladesh has one of the greatest storyline of the traditional architectural development in respect of the geo-physical and cultural context. The conquerors of lands exerted influences on the architectural development and established their building philosophy and techniques on this soil, but in course of time, this architectural style had transfigured and adapted gradually with the local context and culture. Like others, the colonial impact at first halted the evolution of the indigenous trend but the Bengal slowly and steadily began to adapt the new styles / patterns / technologies and thus evolved as heritage of Bangladesh (Mowla & Reza 2000:31-58).

As a regional entity, Bangladesh is a unique in modifying of its culture, more specifically in architecture. All the external rulers of pre-Mughal and Mughal era introduced their significant influences in art and architecture and the adaptation were carried out following the local context afterwards. The reason behind this was related to belongingness of oriental cultures having similar values and philosophy. During the British rule, the ruling class remained as alien usurpers and failed to related themselves with the local people. At later stage, the Bengal Zamindar and upper 'Babu' class, mostly influenced by the western thoughts, constructed new identities in art and architecture and patronized to flourish the new architectural style in their living units.

During the 18th and 19th Century, the new elements introduced by the new architectural styles were the semi-circular arch, the triangular pediment carried over Semi-Corinthian, Doric or Ionic columns, bands and other foliated motifs in

plaster. Column appeared with capitals bearing modified Ionic and Corinthian order; Classical Entablature with distinctive parts architrave, frieze and cornice were applied in different form of structure (Ahmed 1985:35). Later, in the late 19th- and early 20th- centuries, a new hybrid of Mughal and European style emerged in the wake of first partition of Bengal, largely under the influence of Lord Curzon (Ahmed 1985:35,1999:26). Local elements such as hanging eaves, brackets, loggias, verandahs, lattices, kiosks or cupolas were began to appear on the buildings model after basic European forms. Besides the colonial rulers, the local elite in order to imitate the ruling class, tried to follow European models adapted to suit their taste, thus had been producing a hybrid Anglo-Indian or transformed traditional typology (Ahmed 1999).

As the local gentry started to learn English and emulate the sartorial styles and manners of the new rulers, European forms and techniques of construction influenced the buildings architecture of local Zamindar. Predictably, the new styles were most dramatically reflected in the palaces of those affluent. Later colonial architecture rooted in European styles was adapted to suit the climate of Bengal (Ghose 1989). The use or absence or abundance of local forms in colonial Zamindar house depended on the desired image that the feudal lords wished to project (Mamun 1989). Their pre-occupation with western lifestyles was well reflected in their architecture, which featured classical columns, domes with high drums, fenestration, pediments, Roman semi-circular arches, staircases and halls in the centre of the main block with rooms on either side (Banglapedia vol.10:2003). Though these buildings took to a variety of elements and

tastes acquired often from Europe and had much variation in house form, the denotation, classification, arrangement and hierarchy of space; the inherent spirits were basically conventional and traditional (Ahmed & Khan 2004:40). Thus local materials, craftsmen, geo-climate, religious and cultural context were some of the modifier factors that develop the style of Zamindar house form in Bangladesh.

In order to understand the evolution of Architecture and Spaces, it is essential to understand the principles that are inherent in the creation. The main concern of the architects here should be to understand the underlying principles and philosophies behind the creation of pattern and to preserve what we already have and that will make our cultural heritage.

The Zamindar houses of Bangladesh deserve more attention and study, firstly as evidence of the local architectural evolution and secondly as nice pieces and dilapidated heritage of our culture. With this sensation this paper is an attempt to study these house forms with respect to local context as well as the physical documentation.

Rationale

Zamindar houses with rich colonial records have distinct aesthetic values and heritage but are not be positively categorized according to definite tenets of style. This study aims to explore how buildings of Zamindars in British colonial period were evolved as a product of social dynamics, prevailing ideas and aesthetic currents and uphold the image of the architectural development as a whole.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to understand the architectural style and the forces that had acted here to produce Zamindar house form. The study is an attempt to explain the gradual evolution of the Feudal Architecture of Bangladesh under the stresses and strains of different phases of history.

Overview of the Stylistic Evolution

The evolution of the colonial architecture especially Zamindar houses based on geo-climate of the places primarily and secondly it established a tradition in Bengal adapted through an interaction with the Europe and Indian region and beyond. In the diagram (Naqi & Khan 1995) this evolutionary process of architectural style of sub continental context is shown.

The traditions are carried, developed and maintained from generation to generation for thousands of years in our traditional house forms¹. So to understand the origin, as vernacular architecture in this region, those house form is

Diagram explaining the various forces acting on the Stylistic Evolution of Architecture in Bangladesh

justifiable (Islam 2003). In traditional Bengali houses, the courtyard facilitates all household and socio-cultural activities as the focus of the spatial arrangement. It manifests various aspects of life style, values, social customs, culture, climate, location, economy (Mahabub 2003). This prominent aspect played the role of a modifier in determining the form and general pattern of layout in our concerned permanent buildings. So, with this above discussion, major influences could be categorized as follows:

- a) Regional-identity
- b) European-identity

a) **Regional-identity:** In the regional-identity, buildings typically have a deeply curved cornice, while the wall surface, in most places, is plastered. Both the indigenous and traditional typology is fused here harmoniously to present a very pleasing appearance (Mowla 1995). In the traditional vernacular, the fundamental changes in the decoration of their buildings were brought about by discarding the age old art of terracotta and replacing it by plastered panels. The typical curvature of cornice and battlements of the earlier typology was also abandoned in favour of straight horizontal parapet (Ahmed 1985:7, Brown 1942:33-39). This typology was greatly influenced by the contemporary north-Indian styles.

b) **European-identity:** It introduced the design principal of mutual symmetry along a single alignment either from north to south or east to west. Columns and pilasters might be in Doric and Corinthian. Windows might be Venetian with 'serliana' or Palladian window style. The facades were more complicated with the integration of elements of Neo-gothic, Baroque, Palladian or Renaissance designs. Greek and Roman columns, decorated window frames and festoons were common in the design. Ornate facades featured parapets, open balustrades, frieze, cornice and flamboyant gables.

With these above influences the architecture of Feudal / Zamindar houses developed as a mixture of both Regional and European identity. Mowla and Reza (Mowla & Reza 2000:31-58) identified this type of mix up as 'Racial classicism' (late 19th century) and which was described as '...laid to structural adaptation within classical frame. Mixed style /Indian skeleton dipped into European skin/Euro-Indian style'. Those architecture and Spaces of Zamindar houses had created a new style in the architecture with indigenous principles that are inherent in the creation. In most cases, the general layouts of buildings had formal characters of clustering and the houses became a series of rooms with successive courtyards arranged longitudinally which differed from 'European Bungalow style'² that executed by colonial rulers.

Buildings that developed by feudal lords showed more of personal intention (taste, liking and prejudice) than inclination to the grammar of classicism (Khan & Mridha 1996). Locally available technology and craftsman, whom adapted European building construction knowledge, had been flourished their skills and artistic activities rooted in deep of regional identity. In feudal architecture, almost all the elements and features of European architecture were exploited but they were employed with a degree of freedom by ignoring proportion and meaningful associations. The only bold character they hold is the central or symmetrical façade with neo-classical or gothic features as frontage. Colonnade in porticoes attempted but intercolumniation of regular spacing is disturbed and not proportionately tied in horizontal-vertical relationship. The order of column received a peculiar attention. The capital showed tendency towards Corinthian but devoid of 'achinthus' foliage and its proportionate detailing. In most cases the capital was left untreated. In preparing pediment most of the freedom was taken. It was treated in maximum plasticity of personal choice, result of which give varied detailing, carvings and moldings unique in their own merits.

General Architectural characteristics

Location and planning: Compound planning of Zamindar houses depended on local geo-climate context. The most of the Zamindar house had been constructed on the bank of river side for easy accessibility through river transport. The house contented a number of multiple blocks and broadly divided into two parts. One was the outer house containing 'Kuchery' with 'atithisala'³, 'nahabatkhana'⁴ and this area was principally dominated by male persons. These structures were consolidated in nature. The other one was the inner house or 'Andarmahal'. Living unit, sleeping areas and associated service areas were accommodated there and

secured more privacy. Multiple clustered structures were arranged around the 'uthan' or inner courtyard.⁵ Lavatories, service blocks for servant accommodation, stable, 'gola' or store areas were detached from main house blocks. Sufficient numbers of pond or 'dighi' with massive 'ghat' were also constructed in Zamindar house. Sometimes 'indara' or well was founded in compound.

Temple, shrine, mosque or other devotee spaces were significant in feudal houses. 'Tulsi tala' was common in house for 'evening arati'⁶. 'Nat-mandap' and private mandirs were built in some of hindu Zamindar houses. These spaces had important design consideration while building the houses of Zamindar.

House Form: In detail house form planning, several rooms were accommodated side by side in a house block which was directly and independently approached from the verandahs and again these were also interconnected. Verandahs which were originated through colonial culture (King 1984, Nilsson 1968) were the most common in house block and often it ran at the both side of front and inner/ rear part of house block.

During colonial period Trabeated⁷ roofing with tiles and rafter replaced massive vaulted roofs and pure arches emerged. Classical entablature with distinctive parts architrave, frieze and cornice were applied. Verandas opening were typical arches with distinct and prominent keystone at the centre. One of the features of the frontage was openings or windows occupying the centre of the wall panel. In shape, it was a stilted semi-circular aperture divided into lunettes. For ornamentation and decoration, tracery works on windows, rustic works or bond details in plaster, mouldings in cornice, details of the parapet, decorative work, finial or kiosks on pillars and corners of parapets were indicative of European or Indian influence. Cast iron structure columns and Cast iron decorative railings work were often used in Zamindar houses.

Case Study of Teota Zamindar Palace Background of Zamindar Family

Teota estate is seated on the bank of Jamuna River at Shivalaya, a Union in Manikganj district, Bangladesh. The Estate, comprise of large landed properties in the present-day districts of Manikganj, Rajbari, Faridpur, Dhaka Savar, Nawabganj, Munshiganj, Pabna, Thakurgaon and Dinajpur, was the largest Zamindari estate in Manikganj (Saifuddin 1987). This Zamindar family was founded by Panchanan Chaudhuri, (Born 1740), who began his 'career' away from home, in Dinajpur in the tobacco trade (Banglapedia Vol.7, 2003). With the profits earned from his lucrative business, he

Map 01: Location of Teota Palace

started to invest in land after the 'Permanent Settlement'. He acquired his properties at first in the Dinajpur region. Some times later, he returned to his ancestral village, and established himself as the first Zamindar of Teota. A number of members the family, Joy Sankar Choudhury, Raja Shyama Sankar Roy Bahadur, Roy Parbati Sankar Choudhury, Kumar Sankar Roy Choudhury, Kiran Sankar Roy and Dr. Kumud Sankar Roy

Fig 01: Panoramic of Teota Palace, Manikganj

made notable contributions to public life in eminent ways.

The Teota Estate was partitioned into a number of shares around 1914-1920. The Zamindari ends with the abolition of Zamindari at the time of acquisition of the estates by the government, under the provisions of the East Bengal State Acquisition and Tenancy Act of 1950. The big structures of the Zamindar family still survive though abandoned and left uncared since 1957. These are now occupied as squatters.

Architectural Features and vocabulary of form

To study the architectural vocabulary of this Zamindar palace, we may analyze the this in following principle of architecture:

a) Compound & Planning strategy:

The entire complex, comprise of a maze of courtyards, water bodies and buildings, the construction was started earliest at the later of 18th century, and ended at early 19th century. The palace consists of two main parts according to accessibility and privacy; one is the outer house which contents 'Kuchery', 'atithisala', 'nahabatkhana' or entry house and main temple. Public access was permitted in those area and

that spaces were dominated mainly by male. Other part was dwelling houses, these more privet areas were dominated by female.

The complex is surrounded by a boundary wall; some part of that wall is visible at eastern part of the complex. A Kuchery, a Dol-Mancha, three house blocks content court inside and service blocks at rear part are still standing in the ruins. Some of the structures like the two-storied 'nahabatkhana' across the dighi, the Zamindar's 'atithisala' or guest room and some other structures have completely disappeared with the passage of time.

b) Plan Layout: The complex was developed in several phases. Different parts of the complex have different types of use and expression. These physical parts of Teota complex are descried below:

i) Kuchery: 'Kuchery' building, adjacent to the road on north, was owned by the Jai Sankar estate and was erected, according to an inscription, in 1914 A.D (Ahmed 1999: 84-87). It is east-west elongated oblong structure of about 70'-0" x 50'-0" crowned with the double layered 'Char Chala' roofs. The upper layer is covered with brick-red Raniganj tiles and lower layer is covered with corrugated sheets which may be refabricated later. On the Westside adjacent to this structure stands a 12'-0" square pavilion similarly covered with Raniganj tiles.

[This compound plan layout is developed on the basis of Haque, Ahsan & Ashraf (1997) drawing]

Fig 02: Kuchery

ii) Dol-Mancha: The 'Dol-Mancha' or the 'Navaratna' temple, a picturesque square edifice of about 50'-0" base and 58'-0" height, is located on the eastern bank of the pond. The temple rises in three receding stages and is crowned by nine decorated 'pida' type miniature 'ratnas' consisting of multi foil arch. This shrine is ornamented with semi-circular pilaster arches on all sides and on each stage. According to an inscription fixed on its body, it was built in 1858. It was badly damaged in an earthquake in 1897 and was repaired in 1906 A.D (Ahmed 1999:84-87).

Fig 03: Dol-Mancha

(iii) **Living Units:** The main house blocks placed between two ponds on the east and west keeping 'Dol-Mancha' on the west of both blocks. The first one is older palace (marked as House block A) which consist of two-storied oblong block of buildings, enclosing an inner courtyard about 50'-0"x30'-0" covered by a corrugated sloping tin roof fixed on iron struts.

The entrance of the block is through a projected semi-circular porch on west which is now totally disappeared. Ahmed (Ahmed 1999:84) point out that this porch belong as in the middle of the block and originally

Fig 04: Court of House Block A

carried on twelve pairs of round columns on either side of a covered narrow passage-way, gives access to the inner courtyard. The series of paired round columns supported an 8'-0" wide verandah in front of the block, have also now disappeared with the porch. The front verandah on either side of the porch is provided with a series of semi-circular arched openings, each flanked by slender semi-Corinthian pilasters.

The inner court is overlooked on three sides by two-storied blocks of ten apartments of different dimensions while the fourth side on north accommodates the single-storied family shrine dedicated to goddess 'Durga'. A strip of 8'-0" wide verandah, resting on a series of heavy Ionic columns, runs through the entire height of these blocks in front of the apartments. The family shrine (Fig 05) is entered through a 10'-0" wide verandah which is carried on four pairs of Ionic columns, above which runs a highly embellished floral frieze, interspersed with female stucco heads. The parapet above has narrow arched openings. The verandah leads to a wide cella which is entered through three semi-circular arched entrances. The entrances are flanked by three heavy brick piers, each relieved with eight slender stylized Ionic columns.

Fig 05: Shrine

Another palace (House block B) on north beyond the 'Dol-Mancha' about 100' long, faces west and is entered through a porch in the middle of the block. The porch has three pointed arched openings influence of gothic in front which are plastered all over with cement. It leads to an oblong inner court through a covered passage surrounded on all sides with single-storied blocks of buildings except the south which accommodates a two-storied structure. An eight feet wide strip of verandah runs the entire front of about fifteen apartments which is carried on plain brick pillars on the

Fig 06: Front of House Block B

ground floor, while the balcony of the upper floor rests on a series of semi-Corinthian columns (1'-6" dia) with octagonal shafts. Both semi-circular and two-centred pointed arches have been used to cover the short openings in various parts of the buildings.

The small family shrine is located on the north wing. A ten feet wide verandah, resting on six semi-Corinthian cast-iron slender columns with floral spandrels, gives access to the sanctuary. The sanctuary is entered through five semi-circular arched entrances, the spandrels of which are very attractively embellished with floral plaster scrolls. Above this a large floral plaster scroll decorates the temple wall beneath the parallel bands of foliated friezes. The facade of the shrine with a series of semi-circular arches above the openings, daintily decorated with floral scrolls and the supporting pillars relieved with rows of slender semi-Corinthian or semi-Ionic pilasters.

(iv) **Services:** Beyond this two blocks, another two blocks (House block C & services) of two-storied buildings at the back on either side. House block C contents an oblong court inside and services block remain simple arcaded opening. The entire palace area is enclosed by a dilapidated boundary wall.

Fig 07: Service blocks

c) Materials and Construction technique

The house is built mainly of brick and lime surki⁸ with local construction technique. The exterior and interior is plainly plastered except the house B where exposed red bricks were used as surface treatment. Roof construction system varies in different blocks of this Zamindar house and which indicate the different construction period of different phases. In older house blocks, the roofs are built with wooden beams and rafters covered with clay roof tiles. In house block B, factory made steel beams and rafters replaced wooden beams in roof construction system. Lavatory and other small span roofs are vaulted derived from Mughal architecture. The courtyard of block A has been covered by a corrugated sloping tin roof (CI) fixed on iron struts. Door and window openings were supported either by segmented or round arches or by lintels. Following table 01 shows a brief construction technique of the house.

Fig 08: Roofing System showing Rafter, Clay tiles & Lime terracing

Table 01- Construction system of the components

Sl.	Component	Construction system
1.	Foundation	Stepped and spread foundation may be on small piling.
2.	Exterior wall	About 24" thick load bearing walls, Corinthian and composite type of load bearing and non-load bearing decorative columns, cast iron and brick columns.
3.	Partition walls	Either 15" or 10" load bearing walls
4.	Floor	Wooden Rafter or iron joist, flat bar with clay brick tiles and lime flooring
5.	Opening	Archade, colonnade and lintel
6.	Roof	Timber beam, rafter or iron joist, flat bar with clay brick tiles and lime concrete, lime terracing. CI sheet with iron struts
7.	Moulding and Projection.	Lime concrete, brick, used iron bar inside as needed.
8.	Door and window	Wooden panels, iron hinges, bolts etc.

Table-02- Building Materials

Sl.	Component/element	Materials
01	Foundation	Lime concrete buck
02	Wall	Brick
03	Column	Brick, steel, limber
04	Pier	Brick
05	Floor	Brick, lime concrete, lime mortar
06	Arch	Brick
07	Lintel	Brick, timber, steel angel, flat bar, joist
08	Beam	Timber, Joist
09	Rafter	Timber, Steel angle, flat bar
10	Roof	brick, clay tiles, lime,
11	Door and window frame	Timber
12	Door/window shutter	Wood, Steel plain sheet
13	Stair	Brick, timber, steel or iron
14	Parapet	Brick

Table - 03- Finish materials

Sl.	Component/element	Materials
01	Floor	Neat lime finish, stone, timber, color, red oxide
02	Wall surface	Lime plaster, exposed bricks, clay tiles, 'Alpana' works
03	Ceiling	plaster, wood, steel
04	Door and window shutter	Wood, glass
05	Balustrade/railing	Lime concrete, brick masonry, wood, steel/ cast iron

Table - 04: Materials for ornamentation

Sl.	Component/element	Materials
01	Wall surface	Plaster/ mortar, lime concrete, brick, terrazzo, coloring ingredient
02	Column base	Brick, lime concrete, lime mortar, steel,
03	Capital	Brick, lime concrete, lime mortar steel,
04	Rusticated block	Brick, lime mortar , lime concrete
05	Moulding/ projection	lime concrete, lime mortar,
06	Band	Brick, lime mortar, lime concrete
07	Bracket	Lime concrete, cement mortar, steel, wood
08	Dentil	Brick, lime mortar
09	Spout	Burn clay pipe, cast iron pipe, lime mortar liming
10	Drop	Wood, plain sheet, C.I. sheet, tinted glass,
11	Ceiling	Lime mortar, wooden plank

The building materials used here are mainly brick, lime concrete, clay roof tiles, timber, steel and cast-iron. Materials used in construction may be categorized into three groups (a) building materials (table-02) (b) finish materials (table-03) and (c) materials for ornamentation (table-04). For the better understanding of the materials used in the different components and elements are shown below:

d) Exterior Façade

The stylistic approach acknowledges that the Teota Palace is not just a craft, rather it is a house form that reflects the philosophy of intellectual currents hopes and aspiration of its own time with the owner's and the designer's thoughts.

The facade treatment of this house is the arcaded or colonnaded that similar of renaissance architecture found almost in each type of Zamindar houses. The spans of openings were followed by a module. Giant columns are marking the double height giving the super scale.

It is marked difference is found in the treatment of front with other facades. Usually the front facades in all cases are carefully treated and richly decorated. Symmetry as a theoretical requirement in colonial design, front façade of each block of Teota palace is visualized in three parts that called 'Tripartition' (Tzonis & Lefaivre 1986). The form of centrality is achieved by placing the entry portico and placing similar types of elements of two sides of the centre.

The older block (House block A) is visualized neo-classical style rather other block (House block B) is seemed gothic features with two pointed arch openings. Hanging continues verandah supported by iron brackets, sloping shade upon verandah and red brick color give a unique look for house block B. Both of the houses are well proportionate both in length of the facades and in height that gives the harmony of composition and scale balance.

e) Ornamentation

The concept of ornamentation and decoration includes both the structural and non-structural decorative elements. The socio-economic aspect, life, religion, aesthetic sense etc, influenced the decoration and ornamentation of the houses. The following four styles are identified in the ornamentation of the houses.

- Ornamentation by built-form
- Ornamentation by structural element
- Ornamentation by decorative element
- Ornamentation by surface decorator.

The visual design elements and their organization including ornamentation are ordered can be best considered in terms of the styles of facade treatment, principles of solid-void relationship, balance, proportion, scale, continually, order and dominance and style in ornamentation. Various elements such as line and band, projection, dentil, tablet, texture, jali works and wood carving floral elements, sculpture, color etc are used in different parts of houses to decorate the Teota Palace.

f) Components/ Elements of Architecture

The elements of architecture used at Teota palace show gradually development of built form with period of time. Following Table (05) may help to understand the influences or the origin of the component/ elements that derived from either European background or from Indian sub-continental architecture tradition.

Concluding Remarks

Historical structures are in fact living legacies which help us to understand the structure itself, technologies, attitudes behind construction and socio-cultural events of that certain era and constitutes an intrinsic and valuable part of cultural heritage. Likewise these Zamindar Palaces are part of our

Table- 05- Elements of architectural Design

Sl	Component/clement	Remarks		Component/clement	Remarks
01		Arch Located: Block Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
03		Capital Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
05		Capital Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
07		Roofing System Located: Block A Influence: (Trabeated), Europe			
09		Roofing System Located: Block B Influence: Europe			
11		Cornice Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
13		Cornice Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			

Sl	Component/element	Remarks	Component/element	Remarks	
15		Cornice Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
17		Metal Work Located: Block B Influence: Neo-classical, Europe			
19					Located: Block A Influence: Neo-classical, Europe
20					Located: Block A Influence: Neo-classical, Europe

heritage but due to ignorance and proper preservation, those are disappearing rapidly from our soil. Thorough study and documentation are also absent to make the linkage with our past. There is an urgent need to develop new appropriate knowledge linkages with the past and at the same time relevant to the present.

As a remarkable entity, Teota palace upholds the major architectural vocabulary of development of Zamindar house form. This endeavor should be for an appropriate inventiveness with coexisting awareness are needed by the government, non government agency, local people, professional bodies and others towards the historical and cultural context of Zamindar palaces.

Notes

1. Examples of that kind of buildings are indigenous village huts.
2. Consolidated dwelling block where living unit integrated into one mass with front lawn and backyard service area.
3. Guest room
4. Entry house
5. Court may be enclosed all side or two or three sides by build-structure.
6. Evening worship

7. Column and lintel system.

8. Lime mixture with brick chips and other gradients used during colonial period.

সারসংক্ষেপ

উপনিবেশ সময়কালে উপমহাদেশের আর্থসামাজিক ও অর্থনৈতিক পরিকাঠামো পরিবর্তনের পাশাপাশি স্থাপত্য ক্ষেত্রেও নব্যযুগের সূচনা হয়। বিশেষ করে বাংলায় এই পরিবর্তন ছিল লক্ষণীয়। ব্রিটিশ তথা ইউরোপীয় আধিপত্য বিস্তারের সূতিকাগার হিসেবে নয় বরং এতদঞ্চলের নদীমাতৃক অর্থনীতি ও জলবায়ুগত কারণে উল্লেখিত সময়ের বাংলার স্থাপত্যে ইউরোপীয় ধ্যানধারণার একটি অভিযোজিত রূপের বহিঃপ্রকাশ দেখা যায়। এক্ষেত্রে বিশেষভাবে উল্লেখ করা যায় বাংলার জমিদার বাড়িগুলোর কথা। শুধু দেশজ উপাদান ও ইউরোপীয় চিন্তাধারার সংমিশ্রণ নয় বরং উপনিবেশ-সময়কালের এই অনন্য স্থাপত্যগুলোতে ফুটে উঠেছে মোগল ও মোগল-পূর্বকর্তী ধারার বৈশিষ্ট্যসমূহ। আলোচ্য গবেষণায় এই স্থাপত্যকাঠামোর একটি প্রতিনিধিত্বশীল উদাহরণ হিসেবে মানিকগঞ্জ জেলার তেওতা জমিদার বাড়ির ঐতিহাসিক প্রেক্ষাপট, স্থাপত্যিক বিন্যাস ও বৈশিষ্ট্যসমূহ আলোচনা করা হয়েছে। আলোচ্য জমিদার বাড়িকে গবেষণার সুবিধার্থে কয়েকটি ব্লকে বিভক্ত করে প্রতিটি অংশের স্থাপত্যিক বিন্যাস এবং বিভিন্ন ধরনের প্রভাবকে নিয়মতান্ত্রিকভাবে অনুসন্ধান করার চেষ্টা করা হয়েছে।

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